

STUDY OF RELIABILITY OF COMPLEX SYSTEMS USING REDUNDANCY TECHNIQUES

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KEYWORDS

*Redundancy,
reliability,
configuration,
series, parallel,
complex system*

ABSTRACT

This research article deals with different aspects of redundancy techniques at various levels in complex systems which are helpful in improving reliability. Redundancy is an alternate mean in a system for completing a given operation such that all means must fail before causing a system failure. There are different types of configurations such as series, parallel, series- parallel, parallel- series, k-out-of-n and mixed configurations for a complex system and redundancy can be applied at different levels. In this article an example of a complex system with series configuration is discussed with different types of redundancy techniques at unit level as well as at component level. It is concluded that mixed redundancy technique is best to improve reliability of the system. However, the use of a particular technique of redundancy depends on many factors such as operating characteristics of components or system, weight, size and initial cost etc.

INTRODUCTION:

Today's competitive environment and increased dependency of people on technology have forced the industries to focus a lot on the highest performance of their systems while maintaining a low cost operation. Reliability of a system plays an important role in performance analysis. It is the probability that the system performs its intended function in a given time interval under the specific given environment or operational conditions. Redundancy is one of the most effective and commonly used methods to improve reliability of a complex system.

REDUNDANCY:

Redundancy is an alternate mean in a system for completing a given operation such that all means must fail before causing a system failure. In a complex system, redundancy can be applied at various levels. Adding redundancy increases the cost and complexity of the system. There are various approaches for introducing redundancy in a system. The use of a particular approach depends on many factors such as the operating characteristics of components or system, weight, size, and initial cost etc.

Here we are discussing some techniques for introducing redundancy at various levels in a complex system:

1. **Unit Redundancy:** The simplest technique is to provide a duplicate path for the entire system itself.
2. **Component Redundancy:** Another approach is to provide redundant path for each component individually.
3. **Weakest-link technique:** This method suggests that the weak components should be identified and strengthened for reliability.
4. **Mixed Redundancy:** This approach is to appropriately mix the above techniques depending upon the system configuration and reliability requirements.

To better understand the aforesaid techniques, we apply all these approaches one by one on an example of a complex system as follows:

Let us consider a complex system with three components C_1, C_2, C_3 in series configuration having reliability $R_1 = 0.95, R_2 = 0.90, R_3 = 0.85$ respectively.

Figure-1.

System reliability in Figure-1 above is given by:

$$R = R_1 \times R_2 \times R_3$$

$$= 0.95 \times 0.90 \times 0.85 = 0.72675 = 0.73 \text{ approx.}$$

1. **Unit Redundancy:** To apply this approach we give backup of the entire system and we get the new system as:

Figure-2.

In case of Figure-2, the system reliability is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R &= [1 - (1 - R_1 \times R_2 \times R_3)^2] \\
 &= 1 - (1 - 0.73)^2 = 1 - (0.27)^2 \\
 &= 0.9271 \approx 0.93 \text{ approx.}
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we see that reliability of the system is increased by approximate 20% as compared to original one unit system.

2. **Component Redundancy:** In this approach each component of the system is duplicated by another one having same reliability and the system is given by:

Figure-3.

The system reliability in Figure-3 is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R &= [1 - (1 - R_1)^2] [1 - (1 - R_2)^2] [1 - (1 - R_3)^2] \\
 &= [1 - (0.05)^2] [1 - (0.10)^2] [1 - (0.15)^2] \\
 &= (1 - 0.0025) (1 - 0.01) (1 - 0.0225) \\
 &= 0.9975 \times 0.99 \times 0.9775 = 0.9653 \approx 0.96 \text{ approx.}
 \end{aligned}$$

We see that component redundancy provides higher reliability than unit redundancy.

3. **Weakest-link Technique:** We know that the reliability of a series structure is always less than or equal to reliability of its weakest component. Thus, system reliability can be improved by applying redundancy on only weakest component. In above example of complex system, if we give backup to component C_3 with minimum reliability then system will be:

Figure-4.

In Figure-4, the system reliability is given by:

$$R = R_1 \times R_2 \times [1 - (1 - R_3)^2]$$

$$= 0.95 \times 0.90 \times [1 - (0.15)^2]$$

$$= 0.95 \times 0.90 \times 0.9775$$

$$= 0.84 \text{ approx.}$$

In this case, we see that by applying redundancy on only one component, we can increase reliability by 11% than original reliability of one unit system.

4. **Mixed Redundancy:** Component and unit redundancy are simple to design and easy to implement, however, they are not best configurations. The last approach is to mix the above techniques depending upon the system configuration and reliability requirements. One of the mixed redundancies applied in above example is that the reliability of weak component is improved first and then unit redundancy is applied. The system will be like this:

Figure-5.

And, the system reliability in case of Figure-5 is:

$$R = 1 - [1 - R_1 \times R_2 \{1 - (1 - R_3)^2\}]^2$$

$$= 1 - [1 - 0.95 \times 0.90 \times (1 - 0.0225)]^2$$

$$= 1 - (1 - 0.84)^2$$

$$= 1 - (0.16)^2$$

$$= 0.97 \text{ approx.}$$

It is to be noted that it is the highest reliability as compared to other cases discussed above.

CONCLUSION:

From the discussion made above, we conclude that redundancy makes it possible to construct adequate and reliable system using less reliable elements. In above discussed example we notice that mixed redundancy technique is best among four techniques. However, the cost, weight, size and complexity of the system increased substantially. Keeping all these points in mind and effect of various aspects of redundancy techniques as discussed above, we can decide as to which type of approach is applicable to make a particular system more reliable. It is also essential to keep the cost and weight/size to minimum and the reliability to maximum while designing a redundant system.

REFERENCES:

1. Balagurusamy, E. (1984): "Reliability Engineering", Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Co. Ltd., India.
2. E.F. Moore and C.E. Shannon, "Reliable Circuits using Less Reliable Relays," Journal of the Franklin Inst., 262, 191-208 (September, 1956), 281-297 (Oct. 1956).

3. Jagannathan, T. "General Expressions for Reliability of Redundant System" IEEE Trans. Reliability, Vol. R-21, p.119, May 1972.
4. Osaki, S. (1970): "Renewal Theoretic Aspect of Two-Unit Redundant systems", IEEE Transactions on Reliability, R-19, pp. 105-110.
5. Taneja, G., and Nanda, J. (2003): "Probabilistic Analysis of a Two-Unit Cold Standby System with Resume and Repeat Repair Policies", Pure and Applied Matematika Sciences, Vol.57, No. 1- 2, pp.37-49.
6. Renu, Bhatia, P. and Kumar, V. (2016): "Reliability Analysis of a Two Unit Standby System for Robotic Machines", Journal of Mathematics and System Science Vol.12, pp.93-100.